

A Review on Multidisciplinary Personality of Private and Government Academic Staff

Antony Lawrence^{1,2}, R. Jeyanthi^{3*}

¹Research Scholar, School of Education,
Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced
Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai-600 117, Tamil Nadu, INDIA.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Physics,
Pope John Paul II College of Education,
Reddiarpalayam, Puducherry-605 010, INDIA.

^{3*}Associate Professor, School of Education, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and
Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai-600 117, Tamil Nadu, INDIA

Abstract:- There are many popular sayings and proverbs to the effect that people do not change. This stands in contrast to definite age stereotypes held over the centuries by the intellectuals and writers as well as by the general public. This paradox is partly carried over into scientific discussion on stability and change in the process of life-span development. As we will try to show, the answer to the question of change depends on what you look for and how you evaluate what you find. The central question to be answered is what changed or not changed the personality particularly during the second half of life, has been in disarray. One reason for this lies in the state of personality research and theory which suggests much uncertainty and confusion. In response to the frustrating atomistic research characteristic of the second half of the century, a revival of interest in idiographic psychodynamic approaches can be noted. Personality may be viewed as the dynamic organization of those traits and characteristics patterns of behavior that are unique to individual. Academic staff personality is straightforwardly and indirectly related to learning and teaching in the affective domain as well as to that in cognitive and psychomotor domains. Personality aids teaching, for communication takes place between teacher and the learner- even in the absence of the spoken word. Research on academic staff personality is based on the assumption that the teacher as a person is a momentous variable in teaching - learning process. This study is exploring the difference between the personality factors and coping strategies adopted by government academic staff and private academic staff which shows slight difference in provided facilities due to which performance difference is also observed. This study has tried to elaborate the difference between the personality factors and coping strategies adopted by government academic staff and private academic staff.

Keywords:- Personality, Government, Private, Teacher, Academic.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is important to study that there is no basic conflict between the biological, psychological, and cultural points of view. It is not a question of which approach is correct or more desirable. It is merely a matter of emphasis and interest. As we know at about disorganized personality, it is that its causes are many sided. Few mental illnesses can be explained in terms of simple causation. Every disturbance of personality involves the total person and grows out of the most complex kind of physical, psychological and sociological interaction. The present study of research work emphasizes the multidisciplinary aspect of the problems of coping behavior and personality.

The word personality stems from the Latin word *persona*, which is referred to a theatrical mask worn by performers in order to either project different roles or disguise their identities. A brief definition would be that personality is made up of the characteristic patterns of thoughts, feelings and behaviors that make a person unique. In addition to this, personality arises from within the individual and remains fairly consistent throughout life. Personality also refers to individuals characteristic patterns of thought, emotion, and behavior, together with the psychological mechanisms "hidden or not" behind those patterns. This definition means that among their colleagues in other subfields of psychology, those psychologists who study personality have a unique mandate: to explain whole persons. Although no single definition is acceptable to all personality theorists, we can say that personality is a pattern of relatively permanent traits and unique characteristics that give both consistency and individuality to a person's behavior.(Feist and Rosenberg, 2009).

Some of the other fundamental characteristics of personality include:

- **Consistency** - There is generally a recognizable order and regularity to behaviors. Essentially, people act in the same ways or similar ways in a variety of situations.
- **Psychological and physiological** - Personality is a psychological construct, but research suggests that it is also influenced by biological processes and needs.
- **Impacts behaviors and actions** - Personality does not just influence how we move and respond in our environment; it also causes us to act in certain ways.
- **Multiple expressions** - Personality is displayed in more than just behavior. It can also be seen in our thoughts, feelings, close relationships and other social interactions.

Personality type refers to the psychological classification of different types of individuals. Personality types are sometimes distinguished from personality traits, with the latter embodying a smaller grouping of behavioral tendencies. Types are sometimes said to involve qualitative differences between people, whereas traits might be construed as quantitative differences. According to type theories, for example, introverts and extroverts are two fundamentally different categories of people. According to trait theories, introversion and extraversion are part of a continuous dimension, with many people in the middle (Penner et al., 2008).

Friedman, (1996) suggests that Type A behavior is expressed in three major symptoms: (1) free-floating hostility, which can be triggered by even minor incidents; (2) time urgency and impatience, which causes irritation and exasperation usually described as being "short-fused"; and (3) a competitive drive, which causes stress and an achievement-driven mentality. The first of these symptoms is believed to be covert and therefore less observable, while the other two are more overt (McLeod, 2013).

The theory describes "Type B" individuals as a contrast to those with Type A personalities. People with Type B personality by definition generally live at a lower stress level and typically work steadily, enjoying achievement but not becoming stressed when they do not achieve. They may be creative and enjoy exploring ideas and concepts. They are often reflective.

The sixteen personality types which are used in assessment are based on the well-known research of Carl Jung, Katharine C. Briggs, and Isabel Briggs Myers. Carl Jung first developed the theory that individuals each had a psychological type. He believed that there were two basic kinds of "functions" which humans used in their lives. The function which someone uses most frequently is their "dominant" function. He asserted that individuals either "extraverted" or "introverted" their dominant function. He felt that the dominant function was so important, that it overshadowed all of the other functions in terms of defining personality type.

The theory of Personality Types, as it stand today, contends that:

- An individual is either primarily Extraverted or Introverted
- An individual is either primarily Sensing or Intuitive
- An individual is either primarily Thinking or Feeling
- An individual is either primarily Judging or Perceiving

The possible combinations of the basic preferences form 16 different Personality Types. This does not mean that all or even most individuals will fall strictly into one category or another. We function in each of these realms on a daily basis, but we gravitate towards our primary functions, where our natural strengths lie, and use these primary functions more often than the less-preferred functions. As we grow and learn, most of us develop the ability to function well in realms which are not native to our basic personalities. In the trials and tribulations of life, we develop some areas of ourselves more thoroughly than other areas. With this in mind, it becomes clear that we cannot box individuals into prescribed formulas for behavior. However, we can identify our natural preferences, and learn about our natural strengths and weaknesses within that context. The theory of Personality Types contends that each of us has a natural preference which falls into one category or the other in each of these areas, and that our native Personality Type indicates how we are likely to deal with different situations that life presents, and in which environments we are most comfortable (Weiten & Lloyd, 2008).

II. PSYCHOANALYTIC THEORIES

Psychoanalytic theories explain human behavior in terms of the interaction of various components of personality. Sigmund Freud was the founder of this school of thought. Freud's theory places central importance on dynamic, unconscious psychological conflicts.

Freud divides human personality into three significant components: the id, ego, and super-ego. The id acts according to the pleasure principle, demanding immediate gratification of its needs regardless of external environment; the ego then must emerge in order to realistically meet the wishes and demands of the id in accordance with the outside world, adhering to the reality principle. Finally, the superego (conscience) inculcates moral judgment and societal rules upon the ego, thus forcing the demands of the id to be met not only realistically but morally. The superego is the last function of the personality to develop, and is the embodiment of parental/social ideals established during childhood. According to Freud, personality is based on the dynamic interactions of these three component. Freud proposed five psychosexual stages of personality development. He believed adult personality is dependent upon early childhood experiences and largely determined by age five (Carver & Scheier, 2004). Fixations that develop during the infantile stage contribute to adult personality and behavior.

One of Freud's earlier associates, Alfred Adler, did agree with Freud that early childhood experiences are important to development and believed birth order may influence personality development. Adler believed that the oldest child was the individual who would set high achievement goals in order to gain attention lost when the younger siblings were born. He believed the middle children were competitive and ambitious. He reasoned that this behavior was motivated by the idea of surpassing the firstborn's achievements. He added, however, that the middle children were often not as concerned about the glory attributed with their behavior. He also believed the youngest would be more dependent and sociable. Adler finished by surmising that an only child loves being the center of attention and matures quickly but in the end fails to become independent.

Another important figure in the world of personality theory is Karen Horney. She is credited with the development of the "real self" and the "ideal self". She believed all people have these two views of their own self. The "real self" is how humans act with regard to personality, values, and morals; but the "ideal self" is a construct individuals implement in order to conform to social and personal norms.

A. Behaviorist theories

Behaviorists explain personality in terms of the effects external stimuli have on behavior. The approaches used to analyze the behavioral aspect of personality are known as behavioral theories or learning-conditioning theories. One of the major tenets of this concentration of personality psychology is a strong emphasis on scientific thinking and experimentation. This school of thought was developed by . Skinner who put forth a model which emphasized the mutual interaction of the person or "the organism" with its environment. Skinner believed children do bad things because the behavior obtains attention that serves as a reinforcer. Skinner put forward a "three term contingency model" which helped promote analysis of behavior based on the "Stimulus - Response - Consequence Model" in which the critical question is: "Under which circumstances or antecedent 'stimuli' does the organism engage in a particular behavior or 'response', which in turn produces a particular consequence?" (Cheney et al.,2008).Ivan Pavlov is another notable influence. He is well known for his classical conditioning experiments involving dogs. These physiological studies led him to discover the foundation of behaviorism as well as classical conditioning.

B. Social cognitive theories

In cognitive theory, behavior is explained as guided by cognitions (e.g. expectations) about the world, especially those about other people. Cognitive theories are theories of personality that emphasize cognitive processes, such as thinking and judging. Bandura, a social learning theorist suggested the forces of memory and emotions worked in conjunction with environmental influences. Bandura was known mostly for his "Bobo Doll experiment". During these experiments, Bandura videotaped a college student kicking and verbally abusing a bobo doll. He then showed this video to a class of kindergarten children who were getting ready to go out to

play. When they entered the play room, they saw bobo dolls, and some hammers. The people observing these children at play saw a group of children beating the doll. He called this study and his findings observational learning, or modeling.

C. Humanistic theories

Humanistic psychology emphasizes that people have free will and that this plays an active role in determining how they behave. Accordingly, humanistic psychology focuses on subjective experiences of persons as opposed to forced, definitive factors that determine behavior. Abraham Maslow and Carl Rogers were proponents of this view, which is based on the "phenomenal field" theory of Combs and Snygg. Rogers(1998) and Maslow were among a group of psychologists that worked together for a decade to produce the Journal of Humanistic Psychology.

Maslow spent much of his time studying what he called "self-actualizing persons", those who are "fulfilling themselves and doing the best they are capable of doing". Many of these people demonstrate a trend in dimensions of their personalities. Characteristics of self-actualizers according to Maslow include the four key dimensions (Maslow, 1999):

- **Awareness:** Maintaining constant enjoyment and awe of life. These individuals often experienced a "peak experience". He defined a peak experience as an "intensification of any experience to the degree there is a loss or transcendence of self". A peak experience is one in which an individual perceives an expansion of themselves, and detects a unity and meaningfulness in life. Intense concentration on an activity one is involved in, such as running a marathon, may invoke a peak experience.
- **Reality and problem centered:** having a tendency to be concerned with "problems" in surroundings.
- **Acceptance/Spontaneity:** Accepting surroundings and what cannot be changed.
- **Unhostile sense of humor/democratic:** Do not take kindly to joking about others, which can be viewed as offensive. They have friends of all backgrounds and religions and hold very close friendships.

D. Biopsychological theories

Biology plays a very important role in the development of personality. The study of the biological level in personality psychology focuses primarily on identifying the role of genetic determinants and how they mold individual personalities. Some of the earliest thinking about possible biological bases of personality grew out of the case of Phineas Gage. In an 1848 accident, a large iron rod was driven through Gage's head, and his personality apparently changed as a result, although descriptions (Damasio et al. 1994) of these psychological changes are usually exaggerated (Macmillan, 2000,2008).

E. Personality theory of Jung

The personality theory of Jung (1971) assumes that people are dissimilar from each other in realistic types consisting of pairs of opposites. The first pair describes the way people gain their energy. Some people are thrilled by interacting with others and are tuned to the outer world of measures. Others are more thoughtful with the inner self and are thrilled by their

own judgment and thoughts. These two boundaries are termed Extraversion (E) and Introversion (I). The second pair in Jung's theory relates to the way individuals recognize and acquire information. These avenues of gaining are termed Sensing (S) and Intuition (N). Individual's principal in the Sensing direction carefully examines information and employ all of their senses in their investigations. They are reality based and are thorough in investigative the data they have carefully collected. Individuals who are spontaneous (N's) rely on their instincts and trust their "sixth sense" to collect information. Two modes of decision and methods of reaching decisions are labeled Thinking (T) and Feeling (F). Thinkers are objective, logical and reasonable, and consider data in reaching conclusions. They are able to suspend their personal feelings when they logically resolve a dilemma. In contrast, Feelers are subjective and thoughtful of sentimental outcomes to precise situation. Feelers consider how their decisions will crash others. Myers and Briggs (1987) elaborated on Jung's theory by adding the Judgment/ Perception polarities. These functions indicate the mode in which people act together with the environment. Judgers (J) prefer an organized and stable environment, and strive to regulate and manage their lives. Whereas, Perceivers (P) are elastic and impulsive and favor to stay open to opportunities as they unfold. Becoming aware of one's own personality type and the personality type of others can be helpful in mounting intra-personal and inter-personal development. Personality recognition has been used for many purposes in various organizations; to forecast a worker's aptitude to fill definite roles, to set up pleasant-sounding relationships, to conclude team effectiveness, and to predict future behavior.

In other words Personality may be viewed as the dynamic organization of those traits and characteristic patterns of behavior that are unique to the individual. Some social psychologists express that personality is entirely a matter of social awareness -which is pointless to talk about anyone's personality separated from the particular people who intermingle with him, get impersonation about him, and use trait terms in unfolding him. A trait is a simple behavioral blueprint - a outlook or propensity to behave in a describable way. According to Allport (1966), a trait (1) is more widespread than a habit, (2) is forceful and determinative in behavior, (3) may be viewed either in the light of the personality which contains it, or in the light of its division in the population at large, and (4) cannot be proved nonexistent by the absolute reality that some acts are incoherent with it.

III. ACADEMIC STAFF PERSONALITY

Academic Staff personality is based on the assumption that the teacher as a person is a momentous variable in the teaching-learning process. Personality influences the behavior of the teacher in various ways, such as interface with students, methods selected, and learning experiences chosen. The successful use of a teacher's personality is vital in conducting instructional activities. Personality aids teaching, for communication takes place between the teacher and the learner— even in the absence of the spoken word (nonverbal communication). The teacher whose personality helps create and preserve a classroom or learning environment in which students feel contented and in which they are provoked to

learn is said to have an enviable teaching personality .Each individual has characteristic attributes of personality which manipulate both the manner in which he behaves toward others and the ways in which they act in response to him. The teacher with invasive dictatorial characteristics, for example, is likely to reproduce them in his relationships with students and in the techniques he uses in his instruction.

There are more than a few reasons for attributing such enormous importance to the personality of a teacher. The first and leading is that the personality of the teacher influences his/her association with pupils. One is aware that faulty/pathological interface patterns stemming from the concerned personality of the teacher can cause gigantic damage to the mental and physical health position of pupils. A well balanced, non-anxious teacher can generate a vigorous emotional atmosphere of learning and would be at ease with his/her pupil. The constitution of our country and the goals set therein, the policies of state governments and principles laid down by them, the problems related to social and economic set up are all indicators towards only one thing i.e. education and teacher are inseparable and so is the role played by them in making the future of India. It is therefore imperative that while talking about education we talk about the type of teachers and the training they receive. Training programmes can enhance teacher effectiveness by training them in empathy and interpersonal skills. The key to the satisfied, successful and effective occupational and professional life is to have those personality traits most suited to one's profession, job or occupation. Specifically, teaching as novel and innovative profession demands certain personality traits to be essential for efficacy and quality performance.

The "Big five "Personality Traits:

- **Conscientiousness:** dependable, hard-working, organized, self-disciplined, persistent, responsible
- **Emotional stability:** Calm, secure, happy, unworried
- **Agreeableness:** Co-operative, worm caring, good-natured, Courteous trusting
- **Extraversion:** Sociable, outgoing, talkative assertive, Gregarious
- **Openness to experience:** Curious, intellectual, creative, cultured, artistic, sensitive, flexible imaginative.

The potential importance of teacher personality has long been of interest to education researchers. Most of the research on personality focuses on the types of people who enter the teaching profession, rather than their effectiveness. Of the studies focusing on effectiveness, all use the teacher evaluation as the measure of effectiveness and nearly all focus on student-teachers. It stated that "good teachers" posses positive personality characteristics and interpersonal skills. It was further found that although "teachers" did not significantly differ on personality traits from the general population, there was a large and surprising amount of diversity in "teachers" personality characteristics when they are examined by sex, level of teaching service, and area of specialization within the profession. Now a days personality makeup carries considerable weight in success of the life. In the present study personality measurement of academic staff is done through psychological tests.

Personality influences the behavior of the teacher in diverse ways, such as in interaction with students, teaching methods selected, and learning experiences chosen. The effective use of a teacher's personality is essential in conducting instructional activities. Students learn from a teacher's personality even if there is no formal interaction between student and teacher. The ideological complexity in understanding the benchmarking and world university ranking system from Indian perspectives appear to be at the infancy stage for now. There is also an arbitrary state of mind of some of educational development sector that all the other sectors of the country should run ahead along with the movement of globalization including psychology, global managerial positions and also the notion of millennium development goal, human rights needs and developmental issues etc.

The personality of the teacher and monitoring efforts are prominent teacher characteristics central to interactional mechanisms in language learning but have not been adequately understood. An enhanced understanding of teacher's personality and monitoring is a pertinent issue. While there has been considerable discussion on the importance of teacher personality traits and monitoring in general, little progress has been made in examining how these critical elements affect student learning. Additional research is needed to explore the topic in greater depth. Moreover, the effects of teacher-student intellectual interactions may be contingent on environmental learning factors such as physical classroom conditions and amenities.

A teacher is a highly valued personality in a society and teaching is considered to be the most sacred and distinctive profession. History is full of evidence about the nations where education has distinguished progress. Work and worth of teachers has brought name and fame to nations. Teachers have brought laureates to nations. The profession of a teacher has never been so challenging and demanding as it has become now. Global emphasis on literacy shows the world's concern for the teacher's role in the development of society. The teacher is seen as a role model in society and is followed by students. Thus, the teacher is expected to become a model of excellence. The teacher has to show respect and care to colleagues, students, fellow beings and to the family. Through vision and wisdom, a university teacher can bring change in students. It is the intellectual worth of the teacher that makes students creative, imaginative, ideological and diversified. The charisma of a teacher's personality encourages students to reshape themselves into better citizens. It is quite necessary to develop a professional attitude. A teacher is expected to produce balanced, calm, satisfied and composed students for socio-economic development of the society. Universities are agents of change. At a higher level, it is the teacher who brings change in student

Teacher's personality refers to inner-qualities of a teacher, observed from the teacher's expression of values, beliefs, behavior, and attitude. There are several key indicators associated with virtuous teacher personality. Effective personal qualities include being caring, fair and respectful, having positive attitude towards the teaching profession, participating in social interactions with students,

being sincere, and practicing reflective teaching. Building awareness regarding the importance of such values is the first step in teaching, which may motivate students

There is also the difficulty of finding suitable techniques for those aspects of behavior singled out for study in special cultural groups. For a variety of reasons it is decided to focus on level and style of coping behavior, which as a parameter of ego functioning represents a core aspect of personality functioning and development around which other more peripheral traits could be meaningfully organized from a psychological point of view.

IV. COPING BEHAVIOR

Coping behavior is conceived here as an individual's tendency or capacity to orient attention in a way which enables him or her to identify in the personal field complexity of goals and sources of conflict whether social, emotional, or cognitive and articulate his or her field by coping affectively and cognitively or by action in a way which safeguards optimal self-esteem and advertisement to changing environmental demands, that is, maximize the potential faster integral development.

Coping behavior may be defined as more specifically and operationally by:

- Availability of free cathectic energy for directing attention to sources of potential difficulty
- Articulation of the perceptual field
- Coping with complexity or conflict, while
- Optimal balance is maintained between the demands of reality. In other words researcher can say coping behavior is also determined by the notion that the readiness to cope actively with challenging stressful situations may reveal itself in different ways and possibly also at different levels of intensity.

Psychological coping mechanisms are commonly termed coping strategies or coping skills. Subconscious or non-conscious strategies (e.g. defense mechanisms) are generally excluded. The term coping generally refers to adaptive or constructive coping strategies, i.e. the strategies reduce stress levels. However, some coping strategies can be considered maladaptive, i.e. stress levels increase. Maladaptive coping can thus be described, in effect, as non-coping. Furthermore, the term coping generally refers to reactive coping, i.e. the coping response follows the stressor. This contrasts with proactive coping, in which a coping response aims to head off a future stressor.

One of the problems encountered in the literature is the multitude of definitions related to the concept of coping (McGrath, 1970; Pearlin & Schooler, 1978;). Coping is primarily a psychological concept and although there were many definitions all appear to share a basic thought that coping is a struggle with demands, conflicts and emotions. This is different than defense mechanisms which the Webster New World Dictionary (1984) defines to be "... any behaviour or thought process unconsciously brought into use by an individual to protect himself against painful or anxiety-provoking feelings, impulses, perceptions, etc." (p. 370). The

important distinction is that coping involves some degree of thought by the individual.

Cohen and Lazarus (1979) defined coping as the action-orientated and intrapsychic efforts to manage environments and internal demands, and conflicts among them, which tax or exceed a person's resources. Later, Lazarus and Folkman (1984a) revised this definition to be the constantly changing cognitive and behavioural efforts to manage specific external and/or internal demands that are appraised as taxing or exceeding the resources of the person. Within this definition is the inclusion of both defensive and coping strategies.

Coping responses are partly controlled by personality (habitual traits), but also partly by the social environment, particularly the nature of the stressful environment (Carver et al. 2010).

A. Measurement of Coping

One of the difficulties within the area of the measurement of coping has been the different approaches to the problem. Two approaches have surfaced - episodic or situational assessment and trait or dispositional assessment. Trait measures of coping refer to an individual's habitual or particular way to deal with a variety of stressful encounters. These traits or dispositions are aligned to the personality of that individual (Cohen, 1987). Trait assessment refers to an enduring property of a person or a disposition to respond in a certain way under a variety of circumstances. Episodic measures of coping deal with the strategies individuals actually use in a particular stressful situation, that is, what the person does in a particular encounter. The important aspect of episodic coping is that it is characterized by responses in which there can be a flow of events.

Trait measurement has been criticized for assuming consistency in coping behaviour (Cohen & Lazarus, 1979). In an earlier study, Folkman and Lazarus (1980) found some stability in the use of coping responses for an individual across episodes but in general, subjects were characterized more by variability than by stability in coping patterns. Lazarus and Folkman (1984b) state that the measurement of coping traits have modest predictive value with respect to the coping process. Furthermore, Cohen (1987) indicates coping traits do not seem to be predictive of how individuals actually cope in stressful situations. As well, since coping is a process, it changes over time. A person may use an emotion-focussed strategy and then shift to a problem-focused strategy or vice versa.

B. Coping style

Coping is defined as the cognitive and behavioural efforts made to master, tolerate or reduce demands that tax or exceed a person's resources. Coping is a process that we as individuals employ every day. We engage in coping when we feel under stress or want to manage a taxing situation. The process of coping involves two components, appraisal and coping (Lazarus, 1966). Appraisal is the act of perceiving a stressor and analysing one's own ability to deal with the stressor. Appraisal can be made in three different conditions: when we have experienced a stressor, when we anticipate a stressor and when we experience a chance for mastery or gain (Lazarus, 1966). Once we appraise a stressful situation we

must decide how we will respond or 'cope' with the stressor, either choosing to master it, reduce it or tolerate it. The coping style we engage in is ultimately determined by whether we believe we have the resources to resolve the stressor (Lazarus, 1966). There appear to be three main coping styles that people employ when attempting to resolve or remove a stressor: problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping and avoidant coping. Problem-focused coping involves altering or managing the problem that is causing the stress and is highly action focused. Individuals engaging in problem-focused coping focus their attention on gathering the required resources necessary to deal with the stressor. This involves a number of strategies such as gathering information, resolving conflict, planning and making decisions (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Emotion-focused coping can take a range of forms such as seeking social support, acceptance and venting of emotions etc (Carver et al., 1989). Although emotion-focused coping styles are quite varied they all seek to lessen the negative emotions associated with the stressor, thus emotion-focused coping is action-orientated (Admiraal, Korthagen, & Wubbels, 2000; Folkman & Lazarus, 1980). The third main coping style is avoidant coping. Avoidant coping can be described as cognitive and behavioural efforts directed towards minimising, denying or ignoring dealing with a stressful situation (Holahan, Holahan, Moos, Brennan, & Schutte, 2005). Although some researchers group avoidant coping with emotion-focused coping the styles are conceptually distinct. Avoidant coping is focused on ignoring a stressor and is therefore passive, whereas emotion-focused coping is active (Admiraal et al., 2000, Holahan et al., 2005).

Although many factors are involved in the development of psychological distress, coping styles have been shown to be a significant contributor. Problem-focused coping appears to be the most adaptive coping style as it is associated with reduced psychological distress. Alternatively, avoidant coping appears the most maladaptive as it is associated with increased distress. (Carver, Scheier, & Weintraub, 1989; Sherbourne, Hays, & Wells, 1995;).

➤ Avoidant coping and psychological distress

Avoidant coping has been shown to be associated with greater distress than other coping styles. As stressors are allowed to fester and grow they can become more stressful, resulting in an individual experiencing increased anxiety and depression. A negative cycle can then develop where depressed individuals may be more likely to appraise their ability to deal with stressors as low and be more pessimistic about future outcomes (Abramson, Seligman, & Teasdale, 1978). This negative thinking may lead them to engage in more passive coping styles such as avoidant coping and thus the negative cycle is continued. In general, clinically depressed participants experience less improvement and greater dysfunction when they engage in avoidant coping (Billings & Moos, 1984). Penland et al. (2000) found in their university study that participants experienced greater depressive symptoms when they engaged in an avoidant coping style such as wishful thinking. Participants were shown to have increased symptoms of anxiety and depression when they engaged in avoidant coping, as opposed to participants that engaged in problem-focused coping. The positive association shown between avoidant coping and

stress, anxiety and depression may occur because avoidant coping fails to remove minor stressors (Holahan et al., 2005). Holahan et al. (2005) showed that avoidant coping is positively associated with depressive symptoms in a ten year longitudinal study. Their study examined the coping styles, life stressors and depressive symptoms of 1,211 participants over a ten year period. Participants were measured for baseline depression levels at the initial testing period, four years later and ten years later. It was also found that individuals that engaged in avoidant coping at baseline were more likely to experience chronic and acute stressors when measured four years later and to exhibit depressive symptoms ten years later. Although Holahan et al's research is only correlational it does suggest that avoidant coping may fail to remove stressors and as a consequence depressive symptoms may increase. An important element of Holahan et al's study is that depressive symptoms were controlled for at the beginning of the study, thus suggesting that the increases in life stressors and depression may have been influenced by avoidant coping. Avoidant coping has also been associated with increased psychological distress in nonclinical populations such as the general population (Wijndaele et al., 2007) and university samples. Crockett et al's (2007) study also revealed strong positive associations between avoidant coping and psychological distress.

➤ *Problem – focused Coping and Psychological Distress*

Problem-focused coping is the most adaptive coping style as it appears to reduce symptoms of stress, anxiety and depression. A number of different populations have demonstrated that problem-focused coping is associated with reduced distress. Problem-focused coping is associated with reduced distress in clinical patients (Billings & Moos, 1984; Cronkite, Moos, Twohey, Cohen, & Swindle, 1998) with the strongest reduction in symptoms shown by severely depressed individuals (Sherbourne, Hays, & Wells, 1995). Sherbourne et al. (1995) found that depressed participants showed greater improvement when they engaged in problem-focused coping compared to avoidant coping. Furthermore, only one baseline self-report questionnaire was used to measure a number of different factors, such as support, stress, coping style and lifestyle factors. The study could be improved by using a specialised measure of coping, such as the Ways of Coping Questionnaire (Folkman & Lazarus, 1988) or the COPE (Carver et al., 1989). Students have lower levels of stress, anxiety and depression when they engage in problem-focused coping compared to other coping styles.

Problem-focused coping is also associated with reduced distress in the gay population. Furthermore, it is estimated that only 30%-40% of gay men become the primary caregiver for their ill partner (Harry & Devall, 1978) thus her sample may have personality qualities or other factors that distinguish them from the gay population. Problem-focused coping is an adaptive coping style to use in uncontrollable situations, such as terminal illness, as it provides individuals with a sense of control. Folkman (1997) found in a study of 314 men caring for a dying partner that participants experienced an increase in mood once they engaged in problem-focused coping. In addition, Folkman showed that participants were more inclined to engage in problem-focused coping closer to their partner's death as they needed to feel an

increased sense of control. Folkman's study suggests that problem-focused coping is negatively associated with psychological distress as it empowers individuals and allows them to set and achieve small goals in situations where they have little control. Although Folkman's findings provide support for the negative associations between problem-focused coping and psychological distress one cannot generalise her findings to the whole population. As a consequence individuals are provided with a sense of mastery and control, thus reducing their anxiety and stress (Folkman, 1997).

Penland et al. (2000) found that participants who engaged in problem-focused coping experienced a greater decrease in depressive symptoms compared to participants who engaged in other coping styles.

Crockett et al. (2007) also found problem-focused coping to be the most adaptive coping style employed by university students. Crockett and colleagues examined the associations between problem-focused coping and stress, anxiety and depression in 148 Mexican American college students. Their study measured participants' level of social support (Network of Relationships Inventory; Furman & Buhrmester, 1992) coping styles, (COPE; Carver et al., 1989), stress (The Social, Attitudinal, Familial and Environmental Acculturative Stress Scale; Mena, Padilla, & Maldonado, 1987), anxiety (Beck Anxiety Inventory; Beck & Steer, 1993) and depressive symptoms (The Center for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale; Radloff, 1977). Their findings showed that problem-focused coping was associated with reduced depressive symptoms. Wijndaele et al. (2007) recently showed that problem-focused coping is the most effective at reducing psychological distress in the general population. Their study analysed the coping styles and psychological distress levels of 2,616 Belgian adults. Wijndaele et al. found that participants that engaged in problem-focused coping had reduced symptoms of stress, anxiety and depression, compared to participants that engaged in other coping styles. Although a significant association was shown between problem-focused coping and psychological distress it is important to note that Wijndaele et al's study had a low response rate (28%), which may have affected the generality of the study. It can also be said that concepts of access, equity, relevance and quality in Higher Education can be operationalised only if the system is both effective and efficient. The higher education policy should be able to enhance knowledge with skills and develop appropriate attitudes so that our human resources becomes more dynamic in promoting the development of the nation.

An additional study by Bouteyre et al. (2007) further demonstrates the negative association between problem-focused coping and psychological distress in university students. Bouteyre et al. were interested to examine both the prevalence of depressive symptoms in French students and the role of coping styles in relation to depressive symptoms. Their study showed that 41% of the 233 students they measured exhibited depressive symptoms, however, participants that engaged in problem-focused coping were less likely to exhibit depressive symptoms. Problem-focused coping appears to be effective simply because it removes

daily stressors. Although daily stressors are only small they have been associated with lowered mood in university students (Wolf, Elston, & Kissling, 1989). Perhaps more significantly, daily stressors can develop into major stresses, thus increasing the potential for increased stress, anxiety and depression (Holahan et al., 2005). The removal of these stressors therefore decreases the likelihood of experiencing distress. In addition, problem-focused coping may be negatively associated with psychological distress as it requires individuals to set and accomplish goals.

➤ *Emotion-Focused Coping and Psychological Distress*

Emotion-focused coping incorporates a number of diverse coping styles that have been shown to be both adaptive and maladaptive (Billings & Moos, 1984; Penland, 2000;). In general, the coping strategies that focus on negative emotions and thoughts appear to increase psychological distress (e.g. venting of emotions and rumination), whereas coping strategies that regulate emotion (e.g. seeking social support, affect regulation and acceptance) appear to reduce distress. The mixed findings regarding emotion-focused coping has been clearly demonstrated in Billings and Moos's (1984) clinical study. Their study analysed the relationship between coping styles and depressive symptoms in 424 men and women entering treatment for depression. Depressed patients experienced less severe symptoms when they engaged in affect-regulation. However, participants that used the coping style venting of emotions experienced greater dysfunction. The mixed findings in regards to emotion-focused coping are also demonstrated in university samples. Bouteyre et al. (2007) showed a positive association between venting of emotions and depressive symptoms in 233 first year psychology students. In contrast however, Penland et al. (2000) found venting of emotions was an adaptive coping strategy as participants' experienced decreased depressive symptoms when they expressed their distressing emotions. The inconsistency of these results demonstrates that it is difficult to ascertain the relationship between venting of emotions and psychological distress. An emotion-focused coping strategy that has consistently been shown to be negatively associated with psychological distress is seeking social support. Wijndaele et al. (2007) explored the relationship between emotion-focused coping and psychological distress in their general population study and found that individuals had lower anxiety and depressive symptoms when they regularly received social support. Seeking social support is also negatively associated with stress, anxiety and depression in university students. Crockett et al. (2007) found that seeking social support was an effective coping strategy for students experiencing high levels of stress, as students reported fewer anxiety and depressive symptoms when they received social support, as opposed to students who did not receive social support. The negative association between seeking social support and psychological distress has further been supported by Penland et al. (2000) and Bouteyre et al. (2007). Emotion-focused coping appears to vary in its effectiveness as it incorporates a number of diverse coping styles. Coping styles that regulate emotion are effective as they prevent people from dwelling on their negative emotions and ensure they take proactive steps to resolve their negative emotions (Carver et al., 1989). For example, seeking social support is effective as it

encourages students to seek advice from others regarding suitable coping strategies in which to engage (Bouteyre et al., 2007). Another adaptive coping style, acceptance, appears to be effective as it requires individuals to take proactive steps to accept a distressing situation, rather than continue to experience negative emotions (Carver et al., 1989). Conversely, emotion-focused strategies that focus on negative emotions are maladaptive as they require individuals to focus on their negative emotions rather than remove them (Billings & Moos, 1984). Coping styles such as venting of emotions and rumination are generally shown to be maladaptive as they do not remove the negative emotions but in fact exacerbate them and prolong existing feelings of distress (Windle & Windle, 1996).

➤ *Personality and psychological distress*

Personality traits appear to play an influential role in the development of psychological distress. Personalities that are more negative are traditionally associated with greater distress, while more outgoing and positive personalities generally experience positive psychological health. The majority of research that has examined the relationship between personality and distress has focused on the "Big Five" personality traits. This research has shown there are significant associations between psychological distress and the personality traits neuroticism, extraversion and conscientiousness. More recently, greater attention has focused on the genetic make-up of personality which led to the development of Cloninger's psychobiological model (Cloninger, Svrakic, & Przybeck, 1993). Cloninger's model postulates that personality development is influenced by both biological and psychological processes. Strong associations have been found between Cloninger's personality traits and psychological distress which suggests that certain personalities may be genetically predisposed to experience distress. Stress, anxiety and depressive symptoms while avoidant coping is positively associated with stress, anxiety and depression. The research surrounding emotion-focused coping has produced mixed findings, with some studies showing it to be associated with increased distress and others decreased distress. This appears to occur because emotion-focused coping encompasses a broad range of coping strategies, each with varying effectiveness.

Although a large amount of literature has analysed the associations between personality and psychological distress and coping styles and psychological distress, less attention has been focused on the associations between personality and coping styles themselves. This can be reviewed in the few studies that have examined the relationship between personality and coping styles. Due to a lack of research, the majority of studies reviewed do not measure personality using Cloninger's psychobiological model.

Lazarus' cognitive-phenomenological theory of psychological distress suggests that our personality may influence the type of coping style we engage in (Lazarus, 1966). As seen earlier, coping contains two processes: the appraisal of the situation, and the subsequent employment of an appropriate coping style (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Vollrath & Torgersen, 2000). Lazarus suggests that our personality influences the appraisal process and consequently

the coping style we choose. Individuals with optimistic and positive personalities are more likely to appraise a stressful situation more positively and consequently engage in a proactive coping style. In contrast, more pessimistic or fearful individuals are more likely to appraise a stressful situation as negative and underestimate their ability to deal with the stressor. This leads them to choose a more passive coping style. Therefore, stress is not caused solely by the situation or by personality characteristics, but by the interaction between the two (Montgomery & Rupp, 2005).

Mosher et al. (2006) showed that participants with optimistic personalities were more likely to engage in an adaptive coping style and consequently experience reduced distress. They measured the personality (Life Orientation Test; Scheier & Carver, 1985) and coping styles (COPE; Carver et al., 1989) of 136 African American university students. Mosher et al.'s results showed that students with high levels of optimism were more likely to engage in problem-focused coping and experience decreased depressive symptoms. Mosher et al.'s findings replicated an earlier study by Aspinwall and Taylor (1992) which found greater optimism in university students was associated with problem-focused coping and better adjustment to college at the three-month follow-up. Carver et al., (1989) also explored the relationship between personality and coping styles in 978 undergraduate students. Carver et al. found that students with high levels of negativity and low levels of optimism were more likely to engage in avoidant coping, while students with high levels of optimism were more likely to engage in problem-focused and emotion-focused coping. The finding that personality may be associated with coping styles suggests that individuals with high harm avoidance and low self-directedness may have a greater risk of experiencing distress as they are also more likely to engage in avoidant coping. As the study of personality and coping styles is a relatively new area of research, no studies as yet have examined whether having both a maladaptive personality and maladaptive coping style predicts greater psychological distress compared to either predictor alone. This is an important area to study, especially as past research suggests that personality and coping styles are associated with each other.

V. COPING STRATEGIES OF ACADEMIC STAFF

Dealing with problems or difficulties in a calm and appropriate manner is commonly referred to as coping. How a teacher copes with stress in the learning environment affects the impact of stress on their psychological well-being and on physiological response. Coping behaviors or resources come in the form of physical, psychological, social, or material factors and help teachers overcome job-related stressors and achieve their valued outcomes with students (Blasé, 1982). Common positive strategies teachers use to alleviate stress include exercise, social resources, avoidance, reading, hobbies, movement, and meditation. These coping strategies used by teachers affect their outlook on the situation, thereby altering the perception of stress. To alter the perception of stress, teachers may invoke inward or outward coping strategies. Inward strategies, such as concentrating on something narrow in the field of stimuli around oneself, include seeking stillness and focus. Outward strategies, such

as exercise, involve seeking connections, distractions, and movement. Although there are many common coping strategies available, most teachers rely on social support, active planning, restorative experiences, and suppression of competing behaviors. Social support can reduce the impact of stressors on teachers' well-being, job satisfaction, and physical illness risk. Teachers seek support from family, friends, and colleagues in order to receive advice, discuss feelings, get emotional support, get sympathy and understanding, and to talk about their feelings. Teachers who have more support within their personal lives tend to experience less stress in the workplace. Active planning, although a part of the normal workload, allows teachers to take their mind off stress and focus on their work. The process of active planning involves concentrating efforts, developing a plan, taking some action, coming up with strategies, trying to take steps, and doing what has to be done in order to keep their attention on the students rather than the stressor. Restorative coping experiences refer to teachers being able to release stress in places away from the school environment. Places chosen by teachers reflect qualities that are helpful in offsetting the effects of the source of stress. The places teachers choose most often that make them feel better when stressed include home, nature related outdoor places, city places, churches, and cafes. These environments are helpful in relieving stress because they provide teachers with sensory conditions, social contact, props, and nature related environmental features, which can help teachers alleviate stress.

Along with restorative experiences, teachers may choose to employ environmental coping resources. Teachers' awareness of possible environmental conditions can be a very valuable coping resource. A person's ability to know the potential surrounding environment can be used as a resource. Their knack to change these settings, in order to achieve personal goals is referred to as environmental competence. The most common environmental resources that are easily available to teachers include time, money, social ties, organizational resources, and physical environmental resources such as locations that teacher's access and use for their spatial and sensory properties. Some people, either intentionally or unintentionally, employ negative coping strategies to deal with stress. Negative coping strategies are common responses to stress and feelings of being overwhelmed. Although these strategies can provide temporary stress relief, they can cause more stress in the long run (Crisis Intervention & Suicide Prevention Centre of British Columbia, 2010). Negative coping strategies can include unhealthy behaviors, distractions, violence, and withdrawal. Unhealthy behaviors such as smoking, drinking alcohol, excessively over/under eating, and drug abuse are sometimes used to relieve stress. Distractions such as television, computer, and filling up schedules to avoid facing problems are common ways to avoid stress. Violence such as angry outbursts, lashing out, and physical violence often come about if a situation becomes too stressful. Showing signs of withdrawal such as sleeping, procrastinating, withdrawing from family, friends, and activities, and disengagement are ways in which people try to remove stress from their lives.

Disengagement refers to teachers giving up on the goals in which the stressor is interfering with. Teachers who are disengaged resort to negative coping skills such as not trying, engaging in other activities, day dreaming, sleeping, watching television, and reducing their efforts in the classroom. Disengagement can be applied immediately and without the help of others, but is only a short-term solution. In the long run, disengagement can lead to teachers having cumulating workloads, disruptive classes, and feelings of lowered self-esteem and helplessness.

Suppression of competing behaviors refers to teachers putting aside all activities in their lives so that they can concentrate solely on work. Teachers have a tendency to prevent distraction, focus more on work tasks, prevent outside interferences, and concentrate more on their thoughts on work in order to suppress competing activities. Lessening the demand of other aspects of life and only focusing on work leads to teachers having an increased perception of stress levels, which prevents them from taking time to relax.

VI. EDUCATION AND TEACHING

Man throughout most of history has been only vaguely conscious of the existence of culture and has owned even this consciousness to correlate between the customs of his own society and those of some other with which has happened to see the culture of one's own society as a whole, to evaluate its patterns and appreciate their implications, calls for a degree of objectivity which is rarely if ever achieved.

Education involves human relationships; human interaction and teaching is no exception. Teachers act as a crucial link between the University/schools/colleges and its students, and tutorials provide a great opportunity for face-to-face interaction between and amongst students and their teachers. Teachers are content experts who must cope with heterogeneous student groups. Good teaching requires appropriate interpersonal and pedagogical skills. Teacher personality is a major factor affecting how teachers communicate and deals with students, and yet it is a largely unexplored context of education. As such education is recognized as one of the critical elements of the national development effort and education, in particular is of vital importance of the nation, as it is a powerful tool to build , acknowledge – based society of the 21st century. Improvement of access along with equity and excellence, the adoption of state specific strategies, enhancing the relevance of higher education through curriculum reforms, vocationalisation, information technology, and quality in research, networking and distance education are some of the main policy initiatives of the higher education sector. The importance of Education for the proper functioning of democracy and socio-economic advancement of the country has been emphasized time and again by various commissions set-up, to update the system of Education especially after Independence.

Education is a process of acquiring and being able to apply knowledge. Education also refers to the delivery/process of learning. Self-awareness is a process of knowing about personal potentials, faculties, dreams, and desires. Knowledge is an awareness of self and surroundings.

Knowledge also means knowing surroundings with its realities, structures, requirements, usages, and their relationships to the self. Once information is blended with personal vision, it becomes knowledge. The efficiency of any system depends upon the teacher vis-a-vis the system of Education has come in for a lot of criticism in recent times. This has set the researcher in the field of Teacher Education to study the phenomenon of teacher effectiveness. Good teachers are effective communicators, what then are the personality traits peculiar to these effective communicators?

The role of teacher in Indian culture has been profoundly explained from times immemorial. The education commissions have repeatedly emphasized the role of teachers in shaping the destiny of India as the crucial role of teachers in shaping the future of our people can hardly be overemphasized.

To be a teacher is to be a member of a special profession. A teacher has to display exceptional empathy, persistence, diligence, sincerity, research orientation, honesty and flexibility as a person. Teachers are the models in the classroom whose attitudes are imitated by the students consciously or unconsciously. Teachers provide direction to the students and are sources of inspiration to them. Thus, the crucial role of teachers in achieving the goals of education is self-evident. Knowledge of the desirable qualities required in a teacher can help the teacher become an effective professional person. He can develop the qualities of mind and personality which predispose him to success in teaching and establish rapport with students which are prerequisite for learning.

VII. EFFECTIVE TEACHING

According to Bhatia (1977), "Effective teaching has no meaning if it does not lead to effective learning". In school, students spend a lot of time in association with the teacher and teacher's behaviour affects the learning situation in the classroom. It would be important to know what is that teacher behaviour which is effective in instilling a love of learning in students.

Researches show that learning in the classroom is an emotional experience, and the younger the people, the truer are this statement. The process of learning in the classroom is accompanied and accelerated by positive affect and relaxed atmosphere. Fear of teachers can inhibit learning. An over-anxious teacher with negative attitude towards pupils may unconsciously transfer his/her tensions and unresolved neurotic conflicts to pupils via his/her disturbed emotional interactions with pupils, for example, he/she may continuously denigrate good pupils, and be overcritical, nagging, cynical, over-restrictive, and oppressive in the class. Such a teacher is also aggressive and hostile. Unresolved neurotic conflicts may force the teacher to be sadistic, and suppress creativity and spontaneity of pupils. An self-centered and anarchistic teacher may weaken brilliant students. Pupils are at the receiving end of these unhealthy behaviour patterns of teachers; and pupils' achievement, mental health and liking for a subject are invariably linked with the teacher's personality (Sehgal and Kaur, 1995).

The ineffective behaviour is the least interested behaviour to achieve the desired results. This behaviour is as like as laissez fair supervision or administration, in which the leader is not ready to take some pain to achieve the objectives of an organization. They are not ready to take some risks for the improvement of organization and not ready to give or adopt some new ideas for variety of change in the organization. When the production of the institution is not up to the mark and students are not satisfied with teachers. They are dissatisfied with the expectation of institution, at this stage in - effective behaviour is there in the institution. Neither Principal, nor teachers and other staff members are ready to take some pain for the

Achievement of the objectives of the institution. Irresponsible attitude of the personnel towards their organization may be called in-effective behaviour. In this situation, performance is not appreciable. So when the objectives of the organization are not achieved the organization itself is affected due to this in effective behaviour. If this situation prevails constantly for a long time, all staff members, including leader will become lazy and irresponsible. This attitude is not sincere with organizational objectives. Hopelessness and disappointments are the production of ineffective behaviour in the organization Teachers become more aware of the aim pursued by teaching beyond their own knowledge area, they understand their role as individuals and as components of a collective mission, and can better relate their own expectations to the programme or institution expectations in terms of learning outcomes. The impact on pedagogy is discernible despite the small number of quantitative measurements. In particular, quality teaching initiatives enhance information technology in pedagogy improvement and analysing student-teacher interactions. In institutions that are fully autonomous in programme design, quality teaching initiatives help teachers and leaders to refine the aims and content of programmes. Instruments and policies that foster quality teaching are likely to be beneficial to research activities. An increasing number of institutions are convinced that they will make quality teaching progress by combining professional orientations and research.

Teaching involves two distinct sets of skills. The first is speaking ability. The second is interpersonal skills. Such skills allow one to create the sort of warm, close relationships with one's students that motivate them to work independently. To become an excellent instructor, one must be outstanding in one of these sets of skills and at least competent in the other. It is very important to find the characteristics of teacher's behaviour, attitudes, knowledge, skills and its impact on the academic achievement of the university students in Pakistan. Therefore, at university level teacher's positive behaviour, interaction with students, professional competencies, teaching skills, parental involvement, students own capabilities and university environment, all play critical role for strengthening the potential required for better academic achievement of university students.

It is a teacher who prepares students to behave appropriately within campus and in the society. Social norms and cultural values are considered part of professional and

social life transferred from a teacher to student. This necessitates academia to become a role model leaving a positive impact on students in and out of the classroom. Teachers are expected to meet the social standard code of ethics such as Social interaction, Good human being, Good relations with colleagues, Good relations with students, Positive attitude, Passion for public service, Fairness in dealings, Loyalty to country and nation. Attitude towards work reflects professionalism of university teachers. The teaching profession demands:

- Good communication with professional experts, colleagues and students.
- Sound knowledge in the subject and related duties that is to be performed
- Technical skill of teaching explicitly and focused content orientation
- System evaluation and opening a new spectrum of information
- Firm determination & commitment with the profession of teaching
- Refined values and behavior.

VIII. THERE ARE VARIOUS TYPES OF RELATIONSHIPS INVOLVED IN ACADEMIC PROFESSION

Interpersonal relationship, HOD-Teacher relationship, Teacher-teacher relation, Teacher-student relationship. So in order to maintain such relationships, we need a Balanced Personality? A teacher having balanced personality keeps balance in academic responsibilities. A balanced personality is reflected in teachers' professional, personal and teaching decision making. In order to maintain a balanced personality we need Complete care of biological aspects of personality, Adjustment with environment, Balance of psycho-physical traits, Flexible and organized behavior.

A teacher having balanced personality first tries to improve all those abilities that are helpful in developing the character and status in education, such as hard work, honesty, ethics, passion, love, and care. These attributes cannot be explained by an individual verbally, but they are the part of personality. A teacher's professional personality highlights abilities relating to reading, writing, hearing, talking, analyzing, assessing, ordering, formatting old knowledge into new knowledge, producing, and planning.

A teacher having balanced personality keeps balance in his, Physical properties like food, dress and cleanliness, Relevance in physical skills like walk, talk, sit and hold, Emotional properties like character, feelings and emotions, Mental faculties like knowledge, beliefs, emotion, imagination, creation, and inquisition, Emotional faculties like relations, emotions, love, and care, Personality speaks through speech, dress, hair, face make up and accessories, hands, and outlook

Every individual is unique in his/her personality. Personality of a person consists of manners, attitudes, physique, mental faculties, learning styles & habits, and social status in the society.

- Construction of personality is related to mental thinking and physical behaviour. The mind designs a desirable concept of personality supplemented with body behaviour or action.
- Different social institutions promote accepted behaviours among individuals; religious institutions family, society and school. Initially accepted or desired behaviour is developed by social institutions.
- Education is considered necessary for social training of human beings and teacher assumes the responsibility of developing personality of the learners through changing and arranging the learning environment as well as presenting her/himself as a role model.
- A balanced personality forbids an individual from adopting any negative tendency or extreme behaviour.
- A teacher having a balanced personality maintains balance in his physical properties like food, dress and cleanliness; creates relevance in physical skills like walk, talk, sit and hold; controls emotional properties as character, feelings and emotions; promotes mental faculties like knowledge, beliefs, emotion, imagination, creation, inquisition; and develops emotional faculties like relations, emotions, love, and care.
- An impressive personality helps a teacher to understand and observe social values and traditions, as well as to mature and mentor relationships with family, friends and society.
- A teacher having a balanced personality develops character and status through hard work, honesty, ethics, passion, love which does not require verbal expression but are the part of personality. Similarly, professional traits of personality relate to the abilities of reading, writing, hearing, talking, analyzing, competing, ordering, and formatting old knowledge into new knowledge.
- As teacher-educators, it is essential to know something about the teacher's personality traits and provide them with the necessary training, so as to mould their personalities into the most effective and efficient teacher communicators possible.
- Education

Education sustains our present and insures our future. Unfortunately, the education scenario in India is very disturbing. The 'EFA Global Monitoring Report 2010' (UNESCO), ranks India 105 among 128 countries, and it continues to figure alongside a cluster of African and a couple of Asian countries, such as Pakistan and Bangladesh, in the group of countries with a low educational development index (EDI). In 2007, India was ranked not only behind countries such as Norway, Japan, and Germany that figured at the top, but also past several Latin American, African, and Asian developing countries.

Private schools, also known as independent schools, non-governmental, or nonstate schools are not administered by local, state or national governments; thus, they retain the right to select their students and are funded in whole or in part by charging their students tuition, rather than relying on mandatory taxation through public (government) funding; at some private schools students may be able to get a scholarship, which makes the cost cheaper, depending on a talent the student may have (e.g. sport scholarship, art

scholarship, academic scholarship), financial need, or tax credit scholarships that might be available.

In government schools the actual quantity of schooling that children experience and the quality of teaching they receive are extremely insufficient. A common feature in all government schools is the poor quality of education, with weak infrastructure and inadequate pedagogic attention.

In India too, a private school is an independent school, but since some private schools receive financial aid from the government, it can be an aided or an unaided school. So, in a strict sense, a private school is an unaided independent school. For the purpose of this definition, only receipt of financial aid is considered, not land purchased from the government at a subsidized rate. It is within the power of both the union government and the state governments to govern schools since Education appears in the Concurrent list of legislative subjects in the constitution. The practice has been for the union government to provide the broad policy directions while the states create their own rules and regulations for the administration of the sector. Among other things, this has also resulted in 30 different Examination Boards or academic authorities that conduct examinations for school leaving certificates. Prominent Examination Boards that are present in multiple states are the CBSE and the CISCE, NENBSE.

Legally, only non-profit trusts and societies can run schools in India. They will have to satisfy a number of infrastructure and human resource related criteria to get Recognition (a form of license) from the government. Critics of this system point out that this leads to corruption by school inspectors who check compliance and to fewer schools in a country that has the largest adult illiterate population in the world. While official data does not capture the real extent of private schooling in the country, various studies have reported unpopularity of government schools and an increasing number of private schools. The Annual Status of Education Report (ASER), which evaluates learning levels in rural India, has been reporting poorer academic achievement in government schools than in private schools. A key difference between the government and private schools is that the medium of education in private schools is English while it is the local language in government schools.

IX. COMPARISON AND CONTRAST OF HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS VS COLLEGE PROFESSORS

There are some similarities between high school teachers and college professors but there are many more contrasts. Academically speaking, both teachers and professors have grading styles and policies, deadlines and due dates for papers and projects, and a sense of compassion. If only I would have had someone explain the differences between the two levels of teaching, I probably wouldn't have given up in high school. There are many myths that college professors are unattached drones that push you through. As for the high school teachers, they are more friendly and laid back. Although, this myth between the two is much of the opposite. The grading styles between teachers and professors are very different. The majority of the grade consisted of test

scores and homework. Homework is a large part of the grade in high school, which is hard for some people if they don't have the resources or someone at home to help them. Then there are the tests; if you failed you just didn't pass. You are not given the opportunity to go back and fix mistakes or show you really understood the material. There is no going back and going over your mistakes or showing that you really did know what you were doing. Neither you are allowed the chance to gain extra points, once you turned in your assignment or test it was done. Trying to obtain a few extra points in the process, when it is done it is done. Class participation wasn't a big requirement. It almost seem as if your very presence in the class made a difference.

X. BEHAVIOUR OF PRIVATE AND GOVT. ACADEMIC STAFF

Education is necessary for the personality grooming of individual, so society had established separate formal institutes for that purpose. These institutes are having the triangle of three main pillars; consisted on Teachers, Students and Curriculum. Without teachers, educational process is impossible as flow of knowledge for the development of students is from teachers to student side. They have assigned by the divine duty of transmitting knowledge to the unknowns (students). Their work is too much curious and purposeful. Teachers are like the role models for students and that is why they can easily mold the new generation towards the better life. But for dedicatedly working its necessary to provide facilitated and relaxed environment to our teachers, tens or strict disciplinary environment results in the worse out put and bad heartedness by their profession. This research study is going to elaborate the difference between the personality factors and coping strategies adopted by government teachers and private college teachers.

Teachers are the most essential part of educational system. They are considered as responsible for the development of students and promote skills in them. Myra pollac (1997) (1) quoted the words of Einstein that it is the supreme art of the teacher to awaken joy in creative expression and knowledge. They have the duty to train the new generation and guide them for future. Mishra (2005) said that the teacher who requires instincts makes them socially acceptable, inculcates values, provokes and develops capabilities of man to their fullest and best. T.K.Hemchand (2009) spoke that a teacher in relation to peoples has to act essentially as a friend, philosopher and guide. For the better development of students it's necessary to be professionally satisfied and relaxed, while this satisfaction is possible when the teacher enjoys a facilitated environment. Here in Jharkhand we are having two types of system in education namely public sector and private sector institutions. Teachers of both sectors need different facilities for the competency in their teaching. The research study is exploring the difference between the personality factors and coping strategies adopted by government teachers and private college teachers which shows slight difference in provided facilities due to which performance difference is also observed.

While government college teachers have better job conditions and satisfaction levels, city private colleges have better results, according to a study conducted by a team of researchers at Punjab University. The survey, conducted by the varsity's Life Long Learning and Extension Department, has further revealed that female teachers perform better on effectiveness scales and express more job satisfaction than their male counterparts.

It is also pointed out that teachers of government colleges are found to be more disengaged in their work than their counterparts. It shows that teachers of government colleges have a greater tendency to be not in so much in gear of the task at hand as private colleges are. They are more "not in it" than teachers of private colleges. It seems that the climate of government colleges is though loaded with human factors, but is not so task-oriented as the climate of private school is. The result revealed on alienation dimension means that the behavior patterns among the group including the leader (the principal) are characterized equally as formal and impersonal in both type of colleges. In both types of schools principals' go by the book and adhere to policies rather than dealing with teachers in an informal, face to face situation. It also indicates the emotional closeness or distance between the principal and the teacher is equal in both types of schools.

Intimacy as an important dimension in the climate of each type of colleges works on equal feeling as no significant difference was found between private and government teachers on this dimension. It can be said that teachers of both types of colleges either private or government have had same feeling of intimacy between them. The teachers of both colleges enjoy their friendly relations equally and they have their close friend among their colleagues. Another dimension was psycho-physical hindrance. On this dimension also there was not any significant difference. Hence, we can say that both teachers are having same feeling of psycho-physical hindrance.

On controls dimension significant difference was found between teachers of private and government colleges. Here teachers of private colleges feel more controls of principals than the teachers of government colleges. Although principals of private colleges might be providing all the facilities and secretarial services to teachers but they might more emphasize on work than on personal relations. Therefore, the teachers of private colleges might feel more controlled over by their principals.

Public Sector vs Private Sector are a debate which seems to be a never ending topic. It is very difficult to take stand for either of these forms of administration. The reason behind that is not unknown but obvious as both provide scopes in different ways. From an employee's standpoint, job satisfaction is a desirable outcome in itself. From a managerial or organizational effectiveness standpoint, job satisfaction is important due to its impact on absenteeism, turnover, and prosaically "citizenship" behaviors such as helping coworkers, helping customers, and being more cooperative. According to Edwin Locke, job satisfaction results from the perception that one's job fulfills or allows the fulfillment of one's important job values. Thus, to redesign

jobs, reward systems, and human resource management policies that will result in optimum job satisfaction and productivity, managers need to know what employees value.

The first allegation that can be put up for this debatable issue is that Public Sector is more divided than organized. What this means is that a public sector administration runs on the shoulders of many sub divisions. For example –human resource has a ministry and has many governmental organizations working under it to collect the data from. This may seem to be organized but ultimately it becomes divided and creates a problem in the long run. A Private Sector is also divided into departments which work closely. They need to have a coherent working structure or else business will falter. The organization and separation of departmental power is very strict. This does not create any kind of rift between the different departments as they work together. They operate on different functions and so cannot over ride each other's functions. Again, Private Sector employees have to be visible and accountable for each and every action they take. In other words they have to be visible in order to promote their business but can work in their own comfort. However, Public Sector employees have to work showing complete transparency to their jobs. They have to work under the public eye. So it can be said that they work with the governmental radar on and under public scanner. It is said that the Public Sector is not clear with its endeavors. The objectives of the public sector are more confusing and indefinite in comparison to the Private Sector. The Private Sector supposedly provides more clarity to their apparent subjectivity. This makes the sector more evident. Well this lucidity could go against the Private Sector as this sector is accused of only profit oriented work. This sector will never take anything until and unless it sees profit in it. This “what’s in it for me” mentality is very dangerous as it eventually does not do any good for the community. The dream of this sector is to make more money at the cost of anything and everything. Hence the need of a public sector arises which can look into and offer its services to the wellbeing of a nation. Apart from all this, there is another positive point for the Government Sector in this contest of Public Sector vs Private Sector, that it has elected representatives. It is needless to say that the Private Sector has no such intentions of using popular voting or veto power to ensure its working. It is private and that is how it has to be treated. No trespassing is surely allowed on the private properties. State and local governments have expanded their payrolls and added 110,000 jobs whereas the private sector has cut 6.9 million jobs since the start of the recession. Public sector jobs are always more stable as compared to the private sector jobs during downturns, but their ability to acclimate the current deep recession startled many research analyst.

XI. CONCLUSION

Academic staff personality is, straightforwardly and indirectly related to learning and teaching in the affective domain as well as to that in cognitive and psychomotor domains. In spite of the common physical features, no two persons are equal in manners and behaviours. Same is the personality characteristic and coping behaviours of people working in different institutional set up (Government & Private). The research would add to the study of differences

in personality and coping behaviours of academic staffs working in Government as well as Private educational setup. This research work will definitely contribute in future for other researches.

Personality recognition has been used for many purposes in various organizations; to forecast a worker's aptitude to fill definite roles, to set up pleasant-sounding relationships, to conclude team effectiveness, and to predict future behavior. The difference in the work culture among the private and government institution setup and also the difference in teaching pedagogy and personality variables among the academic staff of both the set up has aroused the need for the present study. The results might help the HR Managers and the policy makers to bridge the gap and frame strategies accordingly. Thus this multidisciplinary study is useful to policy makers and planners of academic staff of the private and government sector.

The study enable researcher to suggest developing some strategies for development of Teachers personality. Furthermore this research study can be helpful for educational institutions to recognize and realize the significance of these factors for promoting and enhancing effectiveness of their academicians. This study may lead to examining the impact of administrative policies, rewards/incentives and various other factors on the effectiveness of academic staff of public and private sector

In future such type of researches should be conducted to check the level of personality traits and coping behavior difference of professionals of different line of work to see the relative advantages and disadvantages of working in Government sector and Private sector.

In fact to take liberty at the discussion of Government Sector versus Private Sector, it can be said that both are equally important for any nation. It should be Government Sector and Private Sector which should be the area of discussion. A harmony between the two is required for any nation to prosper and grow. It may be interesting to investigate whether the extent of experienced ambivalence is similar, higher, or lower for employees in different industries, occupying different jobs, holding different positions, with different ethnic or cultural backgrounds, etc. Moreover, future research should aim at understanding the causes of difference in personality and coping behavior for further studies. In any case, it is worth noting that the present homogeneous sample has allowed for a rather conservative test of the present hypothesis. Specifically, restrictions of range with respect to predictor and criterion variables are known to limit the extent to which the two variables may correlate. Note also that the rather small sample size limits the statistical power for the current interaction hypothesis. It is concluded that to do the quantitative analysis about personality difference, some analysis on specific case studies must be completed to reach at good conclusion.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abramson, L. Y., Seligman, M. E., & Teasdale, J. D. (1978). Learned helplessness in humans: Critique and reformulation. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 87(1), 49-74.
- [2.] Admiraal, W. F., Korthagen, F. A. J., & Wubbels, T. (2000). Effects of student teachers' coping behaviour. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 70(1): 33-52.
- [3.] Beck, A. T., & Steer, R. A. (1993). *Beck Anxiety Inventory*. San Antonio, Texas: Psychological Corporation.
- [4.] Billings, A., & Moos, R. (1984). Coping, Stress, and Social Resources Among Adults With Depression. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 46(4): 877-891.
- [6.] Carver, C., Scheier, M., & Weintraub, J. (1989). Assessing coping strategies: A theoretically based approach. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 56(2): 267-283
- [7.] Crockett, L. J., Iturbide, M. I., Torres Stone, R. A., McGinley, M., Raffaelli, M., & Carlo, G. (2007). Acculturative stress, social support, and coping: Relations to adjustment among Mexican American college students. *Cultural Diversity and Ethnic Minority Psychology*, 13(4): 347-355.
- [8.] Cronkite, R. C., Moos, R. H., Twohey, J., Cohen, C., & Swindle, R. (1998). Life Circumstances and Personal Resources as Predictors of the Ten-Year Course of Depression. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 26(2): 255-280.
- [9.] Cloninger, C. R., Svrakic, D. M., & Przybeck, T. R. (1993). A psychobiological model of temperament and character. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 50 : 975-990.
- [10.] Carver, C., & Scheier, M. (2004). *Perspectives on Personality* (5th ed.). Boston: Pearson.
- [11.] Cheney, W. David, P., & Carl, D. (2008). *Behavior analysis and learning* (4th ed.). New York, NY: Psychology Press. ISBN 9780805862607.
- [12.] Cohen, F. (1987). Measurement of coping. S. V. Kasl & C. L. Cooper (Eds.), *Stress and Health: Issues in Research Methodology*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons : 283-305.
- [13.] Cohen, F. & Lazarus, R. S. (1979). Coping with the stresses of illness. G. C. Stone, F. Cohen, N. E. Adler, & Associates (Eds.), *Health Psychology - A Handbook: Theories, Applications, and Challenges of a Psychological Approach to the Health Care System*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass. : 217-254.
- [14.] Damasio, h., Grabowski T., Frank R., Galaburda, A.M., Damasio, A.R. (1994). "The return of Phineas Gage: clues about the brain from the skull of a famous patient." *Science*, 264(5162): 1102-1105
- [15.] Folkman, S., & Lazarus, R. S. (1980). An analysis of coping in a middle-aged community sample. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 21(3): 219-239.
- [16.] Folkman, S. (1997). Positive psychological states and coping with severe stress. *Social Science & Medicine*, 45(8) : 1207-1221.
- [17.] Furman, W., & Buhrmester, D. (1992). Age and sex differences in perceptions of networks of personal relationships. *Child Development*, 63(1): 103-115.
- [18.] Friedman, M. (1996). *Type A Behavior: Its Diagnosis and Treatment*. New York, Plenum Press (Kluwer Academic Press).
- [19.] Feist, G., & Rosenberg, E. (2009). *Psychology: making connections*. Granite Hill Publishers.
- [20.] Holahan, C.J., Holahan, C. K., Moos, R. H., Brennan, P. L., & Schutte, K. K. (2005). Stress Generation, Avoidance Coping, and Depressive Symptoms: A 10-Year Model. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 73(4) : 658-666.
- [21.] Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal and coping*. New York: Springer.
- [22.] Montgomery, C. & Rupp, A.A. (2005). A meta-analysis for exploring the diverse causes and effects of stress in teachers. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 28 (3): 458-486.
- [23.] Maslow, A.H. (1999). *Toward a psychology of being* (3.ed.). New York (u.a.): Wiley. ISBN 0471293091.
- [24.] Mena, F. J., Padilla, A. M., & Maldonado, M. (1987). Acculturative stress and specific coping strategies among immigrant and later generation college students. *Hispanic Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 9(2) : 207-225.
- [25.] Macmillan, M. (2000). *An Odd Kind of Fame: Stories of Phineas Gage*. MIT Press. ISBN 0-262-13363-6.
- [26.] Macmillan, M. (2008). "Phineas Gage – Unravelling the myth". *The Psychologist* (British Psychological Society), 21 (9): 828–831
- [27.] McGrath, J. E. (1970). Major substantive issues: Time, setting, and the coping process. In J. E. McGrath (Ed.), *Social and Psychological Factors in Stress*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.: 22-40.
- [28.] Penner, L.A., Clarke- Stewart, A., & Roy, E.J. (2008). Douglas A. Bernstein.
- [29.] Penland, E., Masten, W., Zelhart, P., Fournet, G., & Callahan, T. (2000). Possible selves, depression, and coping skills in university students. *Journal of Personality and Individual Differences*, 29, 963-969.
- [30.] Pearlin, L. & Schooler, C. (1978). The structure of coping. *Journal of Health and Social Behaviour*, 19, 2-21.
- [31.] Scheier, M. F., & Carver, C. S. (1985). Optimism, coping, and health: Assessment and implications of generalized outcome expectancies. *Health Psychology*, 4(3) : 219-247.
- [32.] Sherbourne, C., Hays, R. D., & Wells, K. B. (1995). Personal and psychosocial risk factors for physical and mental health outcomes and course of depression among depressed patients. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*. Vol., 63(3), 345-355.
- [33.] Vollrath, M., & Torgersen, S. (2000). Personality types and coping. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 29(2), 367-378.
- [34.] Weiten, W. & Lloyd, M.A. (2008). *Psychology Applied to Modern Life* (9th ed.) Wadsworth Cengage Learning. ISBN 0-495-55339-5.
- [35.] Wijndaele, K., Matton, L., Duvigneaud, N., Lefevre, J., De Bourdeaudhuij, I., Duquet, W., et al.

- (2007). Association between leisure time physical activity and stress, social support and coping: A cluster-analytical approach. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 8(4), 425-440.
- [36.] Windle, M., & Windle, R. C. (1996). Coping strategies, drinking motives, and stressful life events among middle adolescents: Associations with emotional and behavioral problems and with academic functioning. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 105(4), 551-560.
- [37.] Wolf, T. M., Elston, R. C., & Kissling, G. E. (1989). Relationship of hassles, uplifts, and life events to psychological well-being of freshman medical students. *Behavioral Medicine*, 15(1), 37-45.